

THE EFFECT OF SPEED IN PROVIDING SERVICE, SERVICE OFFICER ABILITY AND QUALITY OF FACILITIES AND INFRASTRUCTURE ON PUBLIC SATISFACTION AT THE BELIAN VILLAGE OFFICE, BATAM DISTRICT, BATAM CITY

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Abstract

This study aims to analyze the effect of Service Delivery Speed, Service Officers' Competence, and Quality of Facilities and Infrastructure on Community Satisfaction at the Belian Village Office, Batam Kota District, Batam City. This research employed a quantitative method with a sample of 100 respondents determined using the Slovin formula and Simple Random Sampling technique. The data were analyzed using multiple linear regression with the assistance of SPSS. The validity test results indicate that all items are valid ($r\text{-count} > 0.197$; $\text{sig} < 0.05$) and reliable with Cronbach's Alpha > 0.60 ($X_1 = 0.916$; Simultaneously, the three variables have a significant effect on Community Satisfaction with an F-value of $36.663 > 2.61$ and a significance of $0.000 < 0.05$, and an R^2 value of 0.534, meaning that 53.4% of the variation in community satisfaction can be explained by the research model. Partially, Service Delivery Speed ($t = 2.253$; $\text{sig} 0.026$), Service Officers' Competence ($t = 10.349$; $\text{sig} 0.000$), and Quality of Facilities and Infrastructure ($t = 3.761$; $\text{sig} 0.000$) have a positive and significant effect on Community Satisfaction. The most dominant variable is Service Officers' Competence ($\text{Beta} = 0.785$).

Keywords: *Service Delivery Speed, Service Officers' Competence, Quality of Facilities and Infrastructure, Community Satisfaction.*

INTRODUCTION

Public service is one of the primary functions that must be carried out by the government as a form of responsibility in meeting the needs of the community. Local governments, including sub-district governments, are required to provide public services that are effective, efficient, transparent, and oriented towards public satisfaction. In the context of modern governance, the quality of public services is the primary benchmark for the success of regional governance. This is because public services directly represent the performance of government officials in serving the daily needs of the community. Public satisfaction with public services is influenced not only by the final outcome, but also by the service delivery process itself. Factors such as speed of service delivery, staff's ability to provide solutions, and the availability of supporting facilities and infrastructure are crucial elements that shape public perceptions of service quality. These three aspects are interrelated and determine the level of public trust in government institutions. In today's digital age and open information, the public is increasingly critical and has high expectations of public services. They demand fast, accurate, and transparent service. Therefore, the government is required to continuously innovate to improve its systems and service quality, not only in terms of regulations and procedures, but also in terms of the behavior of service personnel and the provision of adequate physical facilities. This research is expected to provide a clear picture of the factors influencing public satisfaction levels in the region and provide input for local governments in their efforts to improve the quality of public services. The results of this study are also expected to formulate strategies for improving public services at the sub-district level, making them more responsive, responsive, and oriented toward public satisfaction. Thus, the research entitled "THE EFFECT OF SPEED IN PROVIDING SERVICES, SERVICE OFFICERS' ABILITY, AND QUALITY OF FACILITIES AND INFRASTRUCTURE ON PUBLIC SATISFACTION AT THE BELIAN VILLAGE OFFICE, BATAM KOTA DISTRICT, BATAM CITY" is very relevant to be carried out to provide a real contribution to improving the quality

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of public services in the local government environment, especially at the village level which is in direct contact with the community.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Community Satisfaction (Y) Public satisfaction is a crucial measure of the success of public service delivery in government agencies. This level of satisfaction reflects the public's perceptions, assessments, and experiences after receiving services from government officials. Good public service will result in a satisfied public, while slow, complicated, or non-transparent service will lead to dissatisfaction and undermine public trust in government performance. According to Wibowo (2021), public satisfaction is the public's assessment of the public service they receive compared to their expectations before receiving the service. If the service exceeds expectations, the public is highly satisfied; if it meets expectations, they are satisfied; however, if the service falls below expectations, they will experience dissatisfaction. Similarly, Fitriani (2022) explains that public satisfaction with public services is the result of an evaluation of the interaction between the public as service recipients and the apparatus as service providers. Satisfaction arises when the public assesses that the service received meets the requirements of speed, accuracy, convenience, and clarity of information.

Speed of Service Delivery (X₁) Speed of service is a crucial dimension of public service quality. This term refers to the ability of government officials to provide services quickly, accurately, and within the timeframes established by public service standards. Speed of service demonstrates an agency's efficiency in responding to public needs without sacrificing the accuracy of service delivery. According to Wibowo (2020), service speed is the ability of a public service unit to resolve every request or need from the public efficiently and within the timeframes stipulated in service standards. Speed is not only about time but also encompasses accuracy in administrative processes to avoid complaints or errors. Meanwhile, Rahmadani (2021) stated that service speed is the ability of a public service organization to respond promptly to public requests and needs, as measured by waiting times and service completion times. The faster the public receives the services they need, the greater their perceived level of satisfaction.

Service Officer Capabilities (X₂) The competence of service personnel is one of the main factors determining the quality and effectiveness of public services. In the context of government bureaucracy, competence is defined as an individual's capacity to carry out duties and responsibilities in serving the public professionally, promptly, and accurately. According to Wibowo (2021), service officer competence refers to an individual's ability to carry out service tasks in accordance with competency standards, encompassing knowledge, skills, and work attitudes. This competence determines how effectively government officials can provide services that meet public expectations. Meanwhile, Hidayat (2022) explains that the competence of service personnel reflects their level of proficiency in understanding tasks, implementing regulations, providing information, and resolving community needs efficiently and error-free. Highly skilled personnel will be able to provide fast, accurate, and satisfactory service.

Hypothesis

1. There is an influence of the speed of providing services on public satisfaction at the Belian Subdistrict Office, Batam City, Batam City.
2. There is an influence of the ability of service officers on public satisfaction at the Belian Subdistrict Office, Batam City District, Batam City.
3. There is an influence of the quality of facilities and infrastructure on public satisfaction at the Belian Subdistrict Office, Batam City, Batam City.
4. There is an influence of the speed of providing services, the ability of service officers, and the quality of facilities and infrastructure together on public satisfaction at the Belian Subdistrict Office, Batam City, Batam City.

METHOD

This is a method that is carried out by studying books, magazine articles, and other literature that is relevant to the topic being discussed and strengthening it with theories that are used as a theoretical basis.

The determination of the population and sample in this research to obtain good data, namely:

Population

According to Sugiyono (2020), a population is a generalized area consisting of objects or subjects possessing certain qualities and characteristics determined by the researcher to be studied and then conclusions drawn. Populations are not limited to humans, but can also include objects, events, or values with specific traits and characteristics. The population in this study is all people who live in the Belian Subdistrict, Batam Kota District, Batam City, totaling 92,637 people (population data based on information from Belian Subdistrict, Batam Center). This study focuses the population on the community of public service users at the Belian Subdistrict Office, Batam City, Batam City, because they are the parties who directly experience the quality of service, ability of officers, as well as facilities and infrastructure available at the sub-district office.

Sample

According to Sugiyono (2020) a sample is a subgroup or part of a population. A sample consists of a number of members selected from the population. The sampling method uses simple random sampling, a method of taking samples from population members who are considered homogeneous (of the same type) using random sampling without paying attention to the strata (levels) in the population members. The technique for taking a minimum sample if the population is already known uses the formula from the Solvin technique (Ir. Syofian Siregar, MM, 2019: 34), namely:

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + Ne^2}$$

Where :

n = number of samples

N = Population size

e = The margin of error used (10%).

It is known that the population (N) is 92,637 people and the precision level or error rate is set at 10%, so the number of samples is:

$$n = \frac{92.637}{1 + 92.637(10\%)^2}$$

$$\frac{92.637}{927.37} = 99.9 = 100 \text{ people}$$

So the sample taken was reduced to 100 people, using a random sampling technique.

Research Variables

According to Kuncoro (2020:41), a variable is something that can differentiate or change values. Values can differ at different times for the same object or person, or they can differ at the same time for different objects or people.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

General Description

Geographical and demographic aspects are important considerations for both the scope and subject of research. Geographical aspects provide a snapshot of the characteristics of the Belian Village area, while demographic aspects reflect the composition and characteristics of the community as users of public services. This overview is expected to provide a clear understanding of the service conditions provided at the Belian Village Office.

Respondent Responses and Research Results

The population in this study was all residents of Belian Village, Batam City District, Batam City, totaling 92,637 people. However, this study focused on the population using public services at the Belian Village Office, as they are the ones who directly experience the quality of the services provided. Multiple regression analysis is an analysis used by researchers who intend to predict the condition (rise or fall) of an independent variable, if two or more independent variables as predictor factors are manipulated (their value is increased or decreased). The multiple regression model of Speed of Service Delivery, Ability of Service Officers and Health Support that influences Public Satisfaction at Belian Subdistrict Office, Batam City District is as follows:

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Multiple Linear Regression Test Results

model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	7,786	3,844		2,026	.046
1 Speed of providing services	.046	.054	.065	.861	.391
Service Officer Skills	.882	.097	.785	9,069	.000
Quality of Facilities and Infrastructure	-.134	.090	-.135	-1,492	.139

Dependent Variable:

The Multiple Regression Equation in question is:

$$Y = 7.786 + 0.046 X1 - 0.882 X2 + 0.134 X3 + e$$

The constant of 0.057 indicates that the satisfaction of the Belian Subdistrict Office Community in Batam City District (Y) will increase if the factors of Speed of Service Delivery, Ability of Service Officers, and Quality of Facilities and Infrastructure are considered constant, meaning that there is an increase in Y of 0.057.

Hypothesis Testing

The coefficient of determination (R²) is used to show how much of the proportion of variation in the independent variable is able to explain the variation in the dependent variable.

Model Summary

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted Square	Standard Error of the Estimate
1	.222a	.049	.040	3.35935

- a. Predictors: (Constant), Speed of providing service
- b. Dependent Variable: Community Satisfaction

The coefficient of determination (R²) is used to show how much of the independent variable's variation is able to explain the dependent variable's variation. Based on the regression results, the coefficient of determination (R²) value was obtained at 0.049.

CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTION

From the descriptions and discussions presented in the previous chapters, conclusions can be drawn and several suggestions can be made regarding various efforts to address the various problems faced by the Belian Village Office, Batam Kota District, in the future. This information is expected to provide input and be useful for the Belian Village Office in improving the quality of public services and improving community satisfaction.

COCLUSION

Based on the results of the data analysis above using IBM SPSS software, in relation to the Problem Formulation and Research Objectives in Chapter I, and also in proving the Hypothesis in Chapter II, the author obtained the following conclusions:

1. The variable Speed of Providing Services (X₁) turns out to have a positive and significant effect on Public Satisfaction (Y) at the Belian Village Office, Batam City District. This is proven by the results of the t test where the calculated t value is 2.253 > 1.68195 with a significance value of 0.026 < 0.05. The results of the coefficient of determination (R²) of 0.049 indicate that the variable Speed of Providing Services is able to

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explain Public Satisfaction by 4.9%, while the remaining 95.1% is influenced by other factors outside the study.

2. The variable of Service Officer Ability (X_2) turns out to have a positive and significant effect on Public Satisfaction (Y) at the Belian Village Office, Batam City District. This is evidenced by the calculated t value of $10.349 > 1.68195$ with a significance of $0.000 < 0.05$. The coefficient of determination (R^2) value of 0.522 indicates that the variable of Service Officer Ability is able to explain Public Satisfaction by 52.2%, while 47.8% is influenced by other factors. This variable is also the most dominant variable influencing public satisfaction.
3. The variable of Quality of Facilities and Infrastructure (X_3) turns out to have a positive and significant effect on Public Satisfaction (Y) at the Belian Village Office, Batam City District. This is evidenced by the calculated t value of $3.761 > 1.68195$ with a significance of $0.000 < 0.05$. The coefficient of determination (R^2) value of 0.126 indicates that the variable of Quality of Facilities and Infrastructure is able to explain Public Satisfaction by 12.6%, while 87.4% is influenced by other factors.
4. Simultaneously (F Test) The variables of Speed of Providing Services, Ability of Service Officers, and Quality of Facilities and Infrastructure together have a significant effect on Public Satisfaction at the Belian Village Office, Batam City District. This is evidenced by the calculated F value = $36.663 > 2.61$ with a significance of $0.000 < 0.05$. The results of the coefficient of determination (R^2) of 0.534 indicate that 53.4% of Public Satisfaction can be explained by these three variables, while 46.6% is influenced by other factors not examined in this study.

SUGGESTION

As for the suggestions that The author can convey to the Belian Subdistrict Office, Batam City District, as follows:

1. Speed of Service Delivery
While it has had a significant impact, its contribution remains relatively small. Therefore, sub-districts are advised to continue improving the speed of service processes, such as simplifying procedures, utilizing information technology, and ensuring timely administrative processing to increase public satisfaction.
2. Service Officer Skills
Because it is the most dominant variable influencing public satisfaction, it is recommended that the sub-district continue to improve the competence of its apparatus through excellent service training, improving public communication, and strengthening service ethics so that the quality of service becomes more professional.
3. Quality of Facilities and Infrastructure
The sub-district is expected to further optimize service facilities such as waiting rooms, queuing systems, room comfort, and complete administrative equipment to support smooth service to the public.
4. Increasing Overall Community Satisfaction
The Belian Sub-district Office is advised to continue to conduct regular service evaluations, open a space for public complaints, and innovate public services so that public satisfaction can continue to increase in the future.

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